

Metal Derivatives of Organoantimony Compounds : Reactions of Anhydrous Chlorides of B(III), V(III) and Sn(IV) with Arylantimony Compounds

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The reactions of anhydrous B(III), V(III) and Sn(IV) chlorides with tetraphenylstibonium chloride, triphenylantimony dichloride and triphenylstibine have been studied. Tetraphenylstibonium chloride is found to form ionic complexes with anhydrous metal chlorides. Triphenylantimony dichloride forms adducts with the chlorides of B(III) and V(III) involving chlorine bridges whereas no adduct has been isolated from anhydrous stannic chloride. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, spectral data (ir and pmr), molar conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

TAKASHI¹ has studied the reactions of alkylantimony compounds with titanium chlorides. Ionic complexes of the type $[R_4M][R'_2M'X_2]$ or $[R_4M]_2[R'_2M'X_4]$ (where R, R' = CH₃, C₂H₅ or C₆H₅; M = N, P, As or Sb; M' = Sn or Te and X = halo or pseudo-halo anion) have also been reported both from structural as well as biological activity points of view²⁻⁷. Study of the reactions between organoantimony compounds and titanium(IV) chloride has also been reported from our laboratory⁸ and the formation of $[Ph_4Sb][TiCl_6]$, $[Ph_4Sb]_2[TiCl_6]$ and $Ph_3PbCl_2 \cdot TiCl_4$ has been confirmed. The work has been extended to the reactions of B(III), V(III) and Sn(IV) chlorides.

Experimental

Anhydrous boron trichloride (Hopkin William; b.p. 12.5°), vanadium(III) chloride, stannic chloride (B.D.H.) and triphenylstibine (E. Merck) were used as such. Tetraphenylstibonium chloride⁹ and triphenylantimony dichloride¹⁰ were prepared by known methods. Solvents were dried and deoxygenated before use. Because of the hygroscopic nature of some of the reactants and products, all preparations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. The reaction mixtures were flushed with dry nitrogen gas to maintain an inert atmosphere.

General method of preparation of ionic complexes: To a dry benzene or alcoholic solution of anhydrous metal chloride was added slowly and dropwise a benzene or alcoholic solution of tetraphenylstibonium chloride at room temperature under dry nitrogen atmosphere with vigorous shaking. There was no evolution of heat during the course of reaction. The nitrogen gas was passed for 6 to 10 hr and then the flask was stoppered and kept aside for a day or two for complete separation of the solid product. In case of Sn(IV) complex, volume of the reaction mixture was reduced under vacuum. The supernatant solvent was decanted off. The

compound was washed successively with dry benzene and dry *n*-hexane and dried *in vacuo* (1-2 mm) at room temperature. The analytical data is given in Table 1.

The reaction of boron trichloride was carried out at 0°.

Preparation of adducts: A benzene or acetonitrile solution of triphenylantimony dichloride was added dropwise to a dry benzene or acetonitrile solution of metal chloride under dry nitrogen atmosphere. There was no change in colour or temperature of the reaction mixture. The mixture was refluxed for 10 to 15 hr. The flask, after cooling, was stoppered and kept aside for a day when a solid compound settled down. Excess of solvent was decanted off and the precipitate was washed with dry benzene (2 to 3 times) and finally with dry *n*-hexane. It was dried *in vacuo* at 70°. The analytical data is given in Table 1.

In case of boron, the compound formed at room temperature. However, no compound formed when anhydrous stannic chloride was reacted with triphenylantimony dichloride.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra of the compounds (4000-600 cm⁻¹) were recorded in nujol or KBr in Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Far ir spectra of the compounds (600-250 cm⁻¹) were taken using polythene sheets. PMR spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrophotometer in DMSO-d₆. The conductivity measurements were carried out in N,N'-dimethylformamide on an Elico conductivity bridge, type CM-82T. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined on Gouy's balance.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the quaternary complexes of boron(III) and vanadium(III) indicated the formation of $[Ph_4Sb][MCl_4]$ [M = B(III) or V(III)] from tetraphenylstibonium chloride and anhydrous

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis%, Found (Calcd.)			AM (in N,N'-Dimethyl formamide) mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹
			C	H	Cl	
[Ph ₄ Sb][BCl ₄]	White-crystalline	245(d)	48.26 (49.44)	2.86 (3.43)	25.56 (24.38)	58.2
Ph ₃ SbCl ₂ .2BCl ₃	White	>250	31.84 (32.81)	2.77 (2.27)	42.68 (43.14)	—
[Ph ₄ Sb][VCl ₄]	Green	—	45.16 (46.25)	2.96 (3.21)	21.46 (22.81)	75.4
Ph ₃ SbCl ₂ .VCl ₃	Grey	>260	36.18 (37.36)	1.98 (2.59)	31.48 (30.7)	—
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [SnCl ₆]	White-crystalline	195	47.68 (48.36)	3.14 (3.35)	18.68 (17.88)	114.8 50.3*

d = decomposed ; * molar conductivity in nitrobenzene.

metal chlorides in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 whereas the complex [Ph₄Sb]₂[SnCl₆] was formed when tetraphenylstibonium chloride and stannic chloride were reacted in molar ratio of 2 : 1.

The adducts of the type Ph₃SbCl₂.xMCl₃ [x = 1 or 2, M = B(III) or V(III)] were formed when triphenylantimony dichloride was reacted with the chlorides of boron(III) and vanadium(III). Attempts to synthesize the adduct between stannic chloride and triphenylantimony dichloride were unsuccessful.

The reactions of triphenylstibine with vanadium(III) and tin(IV) chloride were studied with a view to synthesizing either triphenylantimony dichloride or obtaining addition products. However, the attempt was unsuccessful. The solid products obtained in these cases after the decantation of the solvent did not show the presence of carbon. The elemental analyses also did not tally with any definite composition. Further, the products were not reproducible. It could be inferred from these observations that a cleavage of the C-Sb bond was probably taking place.

The molar conductance values of the compounds obtained from Ph₄SbCl and metal chlorides (Table I) indicated them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes for [Ph₄Sb][MCl₄] [M = B(III) or V(III)] and 2 : 1 electrolyte for [Ph₄Sb]₂[SnCl₆]. The conductivity of the adducts Ph₃SbCl₂.xMCl₃ could not be determined due to their insolubility in common organic solvents.

The infrared spectra of the cations [Ph₄Sb]⁺ showed bands in the region 450-440 cm⁻¹ for carbon-antimony asymmetric stretching frequency^{11,12}.

For a regular tetrahedral ion [MCl₄]⁻, there are only two fundamentals which are infrared active, viz., ν₃ and ν₄ which are triply degenerate¹³. In the tetrachloroborate anion [BCl₄]⁻, three weak bands were observed at 1470, 1380 and 1270 cm⁻¹ and two strong bands at 685 and 670 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to 2ν₃, ν₁+ν₄+ν₃, 2ν₁+2ν₄, ν₃ and ν₁+ν₄ vibrations, respectively as has been observed by Waddington *et al* for [POCl₂]⁺[BCl₄]⁻ complex¹⁴. Occurrence of a band at 370 cm⁻¹ in

the anion [BCl₄]⁻ suggests distortion in the tetrahedral symmetry which may be due to the ν₁ vibrations¹⁵. The triply degenerate asymmetric vibrations of the [VCl₄]⁻ ion occurred at 410 cm⁻¹. This value for the ν(V-Cl) modes is in agreement with the value of 406 cm⁻¹ for [Ph₃MeAs]⁺[VCl₄]⁻ reported earlier¹⁶. Metal-halogen stretching frequency decreases with increasing coordination number of the metal in a given oxidation state. This is consistent with the results observed here.

A regular octahedral molecule gives rise to six normal modes of vibrations. Of these, ν₃ (tlu) and ν₄ (tlu) are infrared active. The ir spectrum of the anion [SnCl₆]²⁻ showed a band at 285 cm⁻¹ due to ν₃ vibrations. The assignment of the observed band is comparable with those of other related hexa-halo species¹⁷.

The adducts, Ph₃SbCl₂.xMCl₃ were found to be insoluble in the common organic solvents and their melting points were also very high (Table I). The ir bands of the ligand assigned to phenyl ring vibrations did not undergo any shift on adduct formation¹⁸. The bands at 440-430 cm⁻¹ assigned to νSb-C(Ph) frequency also did not show any shift. Two sharp bands were observed at 730 and 680 due to B-Cl stretching vibrations¹⁴. The band observed at 350 cm⁻¹ in case of Ph₃SbCl₂.VCl₃ could be assigned to ν(V-Cl) terminal vibrations. Another band observed at 280 cm⁻¹ could be assigned to ν(V-Cl) bridging vibrations. Therefore, a hexa-coordinated structure involving chlorine bridges could be assigned to this adduct.

The pmr spectrum of [Ph₄Sb]₂[SnCl₆] in DMSO-d₆ showed complex multiplets in the range δ 7.55-7.85 which were attributed to the aromatic protons of the phenyl rings.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements showed the magnetic moments of [Ph₄Sb][VCl₄] and Ph₃SbCl₂.VCl₃ to be 2.76 and 2.71 B.M., respectively¹⁹ indicative of the presence of two unpaired electrons per vanadium atom.

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